

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EDJETA JOBIR****FIRST NAME: BULI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2011 on Windows 8)

HIGH POINTS IN ACADEMIC WRITINGS AND THE COURSE PACK

1)INTRODUCTION

This is a response paper for the first period of the course entitled ACA-401D-International Academic Writing. It is also the first in the series of a response paper that is required of me as a student of PhD in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD). I am very glad to get this opportunity as a PhD student at this prestigious university, and also venture into the first essay as part of the fulfillment of the course. At the outset, I felt like taking myself back to the early days of my bachelor's degree course where we were given all or part of the course titles that were pretty much similar to this; and thought a bit concerned why I need to take the same course all over again. Yet as I read through the course pack, it was obvious that there needed to be a means for reminding yourself of early course work. In fact, I am very delighted to have taken this meticulous work of excellence that is embedded in this course.

As I venture into writing this response paper, I began with this introduction; and proceeded with the second title, which deals with the importance of underlining the difference between academic writing and the rest. The third title deals with how the course pack helps to clarify confusions. The last session, which is the conclusion part, summarizes what is raised in the paper with minor comments.

2) THE COURSE PACK AND ACADEMIC WRITING

There are lots of thoughts that ring into one's mind, when it comes to writing. What type of writing, and how to start is the first query. One may be interested in writings his/her own autobiography, another one may be interested into to creative writing and the other one may be interested into research paper or book which may be termed as 'academic writings.' Each of them could venture into different areas of concern, and as the body of rules and styles differ, they may follow different rules and methods. I am aware that this course did not make any comparison of the type of writings I referred to, but, implicitly, it is one of the best pieces I ever come across that differentiate the academic writings from the rest. I am glad to have the course pack.

The coursepack, as it starts with basics of essay writing in academic field, provides a well written and best organized items that makes you feel thrilled; understand easily, and at the end, filled accomplished that you are reminded or equipped with the tools that helps you follow as rule of thumb for essay wrings. I especially liked the principles and steps listed to take up your task of writing academic essay. The tables, the flow charts, and the style of presentation are exceptionally marvelous. On top of providing new concepts, even for those who are well versed in academic writings, it helps you organize your knowledge into a set of purposeful topics that you can practically use in your academic life. I am also happy to see statements of advise that I routinely use as my own rules. This tells me how the organizers of the course pack have been so intuitive in developing relevant pieces. One of such rules provided by the course pack runs like this: 'If possible, put your essay aside for a few days before you begin to edit. This gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your work with a fresh perspective' (EUCLID 2015, 4). Thus, I found the content and organization of the course pack very helpful for academic writings.

3) CLEARING CONFUSIONS

Over years and through my earlier course during undergraduate and afterwards, I come across different rules that may seem to contradict. For example, for in-text citation, Turabian Style advises to have author-date style, while the ECULID template prefers the author-date-page style. For long citations, there are other authors that tell you to use a paragraph-like-indentation, if you come across a quotation of over 2.5 lines, which seem to me a bit too unrealistic since, if you follow this style, your academic writing would be full of paragraph-like-indentations. Here I am happy that the course pack clears those confusion and advises us to use paragraph indentation for quotation over four lines only (EUCLID 2015, 19).

The extent, depth, and frequency of using quotation are also another milestone that impressed me. Some writers overwhelm their academic writings with quotation, thinking that it provides them strength to their argument. That has been my apprehension so far. This course provides a clear advise on the extent and frequency of the use of quotation, under the title 'A Few Tips About Quotation' (EUCLID 2015, 21). I found this very helpful. Another related issue is the question that arises what to quote and what not. Lack of clarity on this can put you in risking your writing for plagiarism. The

course tells us that common knowledge is not required to be put in a quotation. The course further goes on asking a very intuitive question as to determine whether a statement is a common knowledge or not. It states that if ideas are repeatedly mentioned in literature very often, you may need not put in a quotation since this indicates that the idea is widely known.

Paraphrasing is another task that students struggle with. One of the challenges here is the imperatives of conveying the same message the writer intends to convey, while using one's own words. Beyond its instrumentality for avoiding plagiarism, paraphrasing, in my opinion, shows the ability of the writer to state the same or similar message of the writer in his own words, which in turn, testifies the extent to which he/she understood the subject matter. The course provides the best example of paraphrasing (see EUCLID 2015, 24), which clearly help a writer to leap in his/her academic writings.

4) MUNDANE BUT USEFUL

The section of the course pack that is entitled as 'Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers' is exceptionally informative one which I really found so helpful. For example, for many writers, especially academia, the use of comma may look very mundane, and trivial. But it makes a lot of difference in clarifying ambiguities; especially in lists that enumerates items. The use of pronouns such as 'I' and 'me,' looks again so simple but can alter the meaning and quality of one's paper since in real academic writing, some level of excellence is required. The use of conjunction such as 'and' in and at the beginning of a sentence seems to appear very mundane but affect the quality of your writing again.

Likewise, the differences and similarities in American and British English, has been one of the confusions among non-native English speakers, especially that of ours in Africa. The same word of similar meaning with different spelling has been one of the areas of arguments among my friends most often. I remember when a friend of mine had a long genre of argument with me as the spelling of 'cheque' and 'check,' for bank papers as opposed to meaning that refer to assuring something through double reference (EUCLID 2015, 40). My point here is that I am very much content with the course, in dealing with some of the issues that seem to be so trivial but makes lots of difference in academic writings

5) CONCLUSION

As a way of conclusion, I argue that the course is one of the best-organized course materials I have ever come across in my previous academic career. It harbors all the high points that a student needs to know. I felt that it could be used as a daily guideline and menu for students who venture into academic writings.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Course pack: Period 1*. Washington DC: EUCLID University Press. <https://EUCLIDuniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.